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Data assimilation methods applied to marine ecosystem models

by

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Chapter 1

Data Assimilation methods

The data assimilation methods explained in this chapter have already been presented by Evensen (1998), and this is a simple repetition of what I have read using my own words and my own mathematical framework!

The aim of assimilating data is to build an estimate of a certain state, when a prediction of this state is known and partial observations of this state are available. Data assimilation methods are numerous, and their application depends on the studied dynamical system. However, their basic concept always involve two different steps.

Firstly, the integration step, completed according to the model equations, gives an estimate of a studied state. It can, for instance, be temperature or current in an ocean model, or concentrations of phytoplankton and nutrients in an ecosystem model. The state may be a scalar as well as a vector. Throughout the report we call this estimate “the forecast”.

This forecast can be improved statistically when observations are available, and this is performed by the analysis step. Let us precise some conditions. If at time t_1 , we have a forecast of the temperature and the salinity of the ocean over a certain spatial domain, and if at the same time we haven’t got any observations, no analysis can be performed. However, if at time t_2 , we have a forecast of the temperature and the salinity over the same spatial domain and a measurement of the salinity at a certain point of this space, we can ameliorate the whole forecast, thanks to the analysis step and sometimes, depending on the chosen analysis method, we can even improve the “forecast” of time t_1 . However, this update is statistical and its results depends strongly on the dynamical errors of the model as well as on the measurement errors.

In this chapter, we would like to present the Kalman Filter (KF), the Ensemble Kalman Filter (EnKF), the Ensemble Kalman Smoother (EnKS) and the Particle Filter (PF). Since the three first ones have the same analysis step, we would like to describe this step, firstly in the scalar case, and then with a more general point of view. Afterwards, we will briefly recall the Kalman Filter results and eventually, we will detail the Ensemble Kalman Filter, the Ensemble Kalman Smoother, and the Particle Filter.

In the following sections, we adopt the notations:

- ψ^f is the forecast state.

- ψ^t is the true state.
- ψ^a is the analysed state, after data assimilation has been done.
- d is the available observation.

1.1 The Analysis

The analysis scheme is normally formulated as a variance minimizing method. We adopt throughout this section a discrete point of view, because it is easier to understand and immediately useful for programming.

1.1.1 A really simple case

States are simple scalars, as well as observations,

$$\psi^f \in \mathbb{R} \quad \text{and} \quad d \in \mathbb{R}.$$

We then have the equations:

$$\psi^f = \psi^t + p^f, \tag{1.1}$$

$$d = \psi^t + \varepsilon, \tag{1.2}$$

$$\psi^a = \psi^t + p^a, \tag{1.3}$$

where p^f represents the error due to the lack of precision of the model forecast, whereas ε represents the error in the measurement (due to the sampling scheme or processing methods used) and p^a represents the remaining error after the expected improvement of the analysis.

We have no means to define precisely the distribution function of p^f and ε . If we want to simulate these two errors, we first need to choose a shape for the distribution function.

Most of the time, we then assume that all the errors are Gaussian distributed, because it makes the maximum likelihood estimate and the minimum variance estimate coincide.

After such a choice, we only need to assign to the two random variables, the values of their two first moments. Further, we assume that the forecasts and the measurements are unbiased. Thus:

$$\text{E}(p^f) = 0, \tag{1.4}$$

$$\text{E}(\varepsilon) = 0. \tag{1.5}$$

Concerning the variances, their values are chosen at the beginning and then computed during the integration step. However, at the very beginning, we cannot choose them randomly, since they represent how much we will trust, either the forecasts or the measurements. *This important problem will be discussed later in this report.*

Right now, we assume we know the variances of p^f and ε either from a previous integration or from our own choice,

$$\text{Var}(p^f) = P^f, \quad (1.6)$$

$$\text{Var}(\varepsilon) = W^{-1}. \quad (1.7)$$

We note that P^f and W^{-1} are strictly positive.

Now that we have the complete distribution of the random variables p^f and ε , we need to care about their covariance. It is physically reasonable to assume that the measurement errors are independent from the dynamical errors. It means that

$$\text{Cov}(\varepsilon, p^f) = 0. \quad (1.8)$$

After these necessary definitions, we can focus on our main point, the analysis. The aim of assimilating data is to take as much information as possible from the forecasts and the measurements, in order to build a better estimate. We now introduce the penalty function, which is nothing less than the sum of the normalised errors squares,

$$\mathcal{J}[\psi] = \frac{(\psi - \psi^f)^2}{P^f} + \frac{(\psi - d)^2}{W^{-1}}. \quad (1.9)$$

The variance minimizing estimate is given by the minimum of this function. If we differentiate this function, we obtain

$$d\mathcal{J} = 2 \left(\frac{\psi - \psi^f}{P^f} + \frac{\psi - d}{W^{-1}} \right) d\psi. \quad (1.10)$$

$\mathcal{J}(\psi)$ is the minimum if $d\mathcal{J}(\psi)$ is equal to 0

$$2 \left(\frac{\psi - \psi^f}{P^f} + \frac{\psi - d}{W^{-1}} \right) = 0. \quad (1.11)$$

In fact, this defines an extremum of \mathcal{J} , but the second derivative would confirm it is a minimum. Eventually, by solving equation (1.11), we get

$$\psi^a = \psi^f + \frac{P^f}{W^{-1} + P^f} (d - \psi^f). \quad (1.12)$$

1.1.2 A scalar case with a 1-dimensional extension

In this subsection, we assume we have a discrete numerical grid with a nodes. On each node, a scalar state is defined. Moreover, observations are available only at certain nodes of the grid,

$$\forall i \in \{1, 2, \dots, a\} \quad \psi_i \in \mathbb{R}.$$

The system of equations becomes

$$\Psi^f = \Psi^t + p^f, \quad (1.13)$$

$$d = H\Psi^t + \varepsilon, \quad (1.14)$$

where Ψ is defined as $(\psi_1, \psi_2, \dots, \psi_a)^\top$, \mathbf{p}^f as $(p_1^f, p_2^f, \dots, p_a^f)^\top$, \mathbf{d} is an observation vector in \mathbb{R}^m , and \mathbf{H} is the measurement matrix in $\mathcal{M}_{m,a}(\mathbb{R})$. We now define

$$\begin{aligned} \forall (i, j) \in \{1, 2, \dots, a\}^2 & \quad \text{Cov} \left(p_i^f, p_j^f \right) = \mathbf{P}_{i,j}^f, \\ \forall (k, l) \in \{1, 2, \dots, m\}^2 & \quad \text{Cov} \left(\varepsilon_k, \varepsilon_l \right) = \mathbf{W}_{k,l}^{-1}, \\ \forall (i, k) \in \{1, \dots, a\} \times \{1, \dots, m\} & \quad \text{Cov} \left(p_i^f, \varepsilon_k \right) = 0. \end{aligned}$$

The new penalty function writes

$$\mathcal{J}[\Psi] = (\Psi^f - \Psi)^\top (\mathbf{P}^f)^{-1} (\Psi^f - \Psi) + (\mathbf{d} - \mathbf{H}\Psi)^\top \mathbf{W} (\mathbf{d} - \mathbf{H}\Psi). \quad (1.15)$$

In order to find the minimum, we differentiate equation (1.15).

$$\begin{aligned} d\mathcal{J}[\Psi] &= - (d\Psi)^\top (\mathbf{P}^f)^{-1} (\Psi^f - \Psi) \\ &\quad - (\Psi^f - \Psi)^\top (\mathbf{P}^f)^{-1} d\Psi \\ &\quad - (\mathbf{H}d\Psi)^\top \mathbf{W} (\mathbf{d} - \mathbf{H}\Psi) \\ &\quad - (\mathbf{d} - \mathbf{H}\Psi)^\top \mathbf{W} d\Psi, \end{aligned} \quad (1.16)$$

$$= -2 \left[(\Psi^f - \Psi)^\top (\mathbf{P}^f)^{-1} + (\mathbf{d} - \mathbf{H}\Psi)^\top \mathbf{W} \mathbf{H} \right] d\Psi. \quad (1.17)$$

Note that the second equality comes from the simple fact that $\mathcal{J}[\Psi]$ is a real and

$$\forall x \in \mathbb{R} \quad (x)^\top = x.$$

We then know that the minimum is a solution of the equation

$$(\Psi^f - \Psi)^\top (\mathbf{P}^f)^{-1} + (\mathbf{d} - \mathbf{H}\Psi)^\top \mathbf{W} \mathbf{H} = 0. \quad (1.18)$$

This equation is difficult to solve directly, because the matrix \mathbf{H} is not invertible in most of the cases. Therefore we adopt the representers approach described by Evensen (1998). Define,

$$\mathbf{b} = \mathbf{W} (\mathbf{d} - \mathbf{H}\Psi). \quad (1.19)$$

Note that \mathbf{b} does depend only on the nodes where the measurements are collected. We now try to express Ψ as a function of \mathbf{b} . Therefore, we insert the definition of \mathbf{b} (1.19) into the differential function (1.18), and obtain

$$- \mathbf{H}^\top \mathbf{b} = (\mathbf{P}^f)^{-1} (\Psi^f - \Psi), \quad (1.20)$$

$$\Psi = \Psi^f + \mathbf{P}^f \mathbf{H}^\top \mathbf{b}. \quad (1.21)$$

Thanks to equation (1.19) and equation (1.21), we can write \mathbf{b} depending only on the measurements and the forecasts.

$$\mathbf{b} = \mathbf{W} (\mathbf{d} - \mathbf{H} (\Psi^f + \mathbf{P}^f \mathbf{H}^\top \mathbf{b})), \quad (1.22)$$

$$(\mathbf{W}^{-1} + \mathbf{H} \mathbf{P}^f \mathbf{H}^\top) \mathbf{b} = \mathbf{d} - \mathbf{H} \Psi^f, \quad (1.23)$$

$$\mathbf{b} = (\mathbf{W}^{-1} + \mathbf{H} \mathbf{P}^f \mathbf{H}^\top)^{-1} (\mathbf{d} - \mathbf{H} \Psi^f). \quad (1.24)$$

We know that $(W^{-1} + HP^fH^T)$ is invertible, P_f and W^{-1} are symmetrical positive definite, therefore $(W^{-1} + HP^fH^T)$ is symmetrical. Moreover, we can write W^{-1} and HP^fH^T as diagonal matrices on the same orthonormal base, so the sum of W^{-1} and HP^fH^T is positive definite.

Finally, we insert the new expression of \mathbf{b} (1.24) into equation (1.21) and get the following set of equations.

$$\mathbf{\Psi} = \mathbf{\Psi}^f + K(\mathbf{d} - H\mathbf{\Psi}^f), \quad (1.25)$$

$$P^a = P^f(I_d - KH), \quad (1.26)$$

$$K = P^fH^T(W^{-1} + HP^fH^T)^{-1}. \quad (1.27)$$

1.1.3 A simple exemple

In order to describe more concretely the effects of assimilating data, let us study a simple case, i.e. a grid with two nodes and one measurement. Keeping the same notations as above, we have,

$$\mathbf{\Psi} = (\psi_1, \psi_2)^T.$$

The system writes

$$\psi_1^f = \psi_1^t + p_1^f, \quad (1.28)$$

$$\psi_2^f = \psi_2^t + p_2^f, \quad (1.29)$$

$$d = \psi_1^t + \varepsilon. \quad (1.30)$$

If we assume there is only one observation :

$$P^f = \begin{pmatrix} P_{1,1} & P_{2,1} \\ P_{1,2} & P_{2,2} \end{pmatrix} \quad H = (1 \ 0) \quad (1.31)$$

Computing $P^fH^T(W^{-1} + HP^fH^T)^{-1}$ gives

$$P^fH^T(W^{-1} + HP^fH^T)^{-1} = \frac{1}{P_{1,1} + W^{-1}} \begin{pmatrix} P_{1,1} \\ P_{1,2} \end{pmatrix}. \quad (1.32)$$

Eventually,

$$\psi_1^a = \psi_1^f + \frac{P_{1,1}}{P_{1,1} + W^{-1}}(\varepsilon - p_1^f), \quad (1.33)$$

$$\psi_2^a = \psi_2^f + \frac{c_{1,2}}{P_{1,1} + W^{-1}}(\varepsilon - p_1^f). \quad (1.34)$$

This simple exemple illustrates two important points. First, the states corresponding to nodes where no observation is available are affected by data assimilation only through their covariance (here, this is the case of ψ_2).

Secondly, if the spatial structure of the errors (concerning the model as well as the observations) is not stationary, data assimilation methods can have quite different results with different observation locations. For this reason, if observation locations can be chosen, and if the spatial structure is not stationary, a preliminary work has to be done, in order to choose the “best” location.

This 1-dimensional extension can be generalised easily to vector states depending on space. Firstly, the nodes of the grid can be seen as different variables of the same state and observations of certain variables would be made. Then the nodes can represent a spatial grid, and observations would be made at certain points only.

Once the analysis step is achieved, we have to explain how to perform the integration step. The integration step computes two different quantities, the forecast state and the covariance matrix of the forecast errors. These quantities are computed from the initial conditions at the beginning, and then from the analysed estimates and analysed error covariance matrix.

Most of the time, the difference between data assimilation methods lies in their way of computing the forecast error covariance matrix. In the next sections, we will note P_k^f the forecast error covariance matrix at time t_k and P_k^a the analysed error covariance matrix at time t_k .

1.2 The Kalman Filter

The Kalman Filter is an optimal estimator if the model equations are linear. We are just going to give the well known results with a discrete point of view. Further details can be found in Evensen (1998). We assume Ψ is a vector state depending on time ($\Psi \in \mathbb{R}^n$). Then, the true state evolves in time according to

$$\Psi_{k+1}^t = \Psi_k^t + F\Psi_k^t dt + \mathbf{q}_k dt, \quad (1.35)$$

while a forecast is computed as

$$\Psi_{k+1}^f = \Psi_k^a + F\Psi_k^a dt, \quad (1.36)$$

where F is a linear operator, and \mathbf{q}_k is a generalised white noise process. We can replace $\mathbf{q}_k dt$ by $d\beta_k$ ($d\beta_k = \beta_{k+1} - \beta_k$). β is then a discrete stochastic process, and if we require its paths to be continuous, it can only be a Brownian motion (see Oksendal (1992)).

Let us just recall a few properties of a Brownian motion, it is a Gaussian process with stationary independent increments. Here, as we constructed this process from a white noise process, the mean of the increments is equal to 0. Moreover, β being a Gaussian process means that all the finite linear combinations $\sum_{i=1}^n \lambda_i \beta_i$ are Gaussian distributed.

We make these few remarks just to justify why we will now assert that $d\beta_k$ is a Gaussian random variable with mean equal to 0 and a covariance matrix equal to Q (The covariance matrix does not depend on time since $d\beta_k$ is stationary).

Evensen (1998) then shows that

$$P_{k+1}^f = (I_d + Fdt)P_k^a(I_d + Fdt)^T + Q. \quad (1.37)$$

The Kalman Filter is limited to linear systems for an obvious reason, it assumes that errors between the forecast and the “truth” (model errors) remain Gaussian distributed during the integration. On one hand, this assumption is useful, since the prediction errors are totally characterized through their mean and their covariance matrix. On the other hand, only linear systems keep the properties of Gaussian distributions.

1.3 The Ensemble Filters

Most of the time, we deal with nonlinear models, and we cannot apply the Kalman Filter. Moreover, Evensen (1992) has already shown that the Extended Kalman Filter (EKF) -a linearized version of the Kalman Filter - could present undesirable properties of unstability. Therefore, more elaborate filters were developed, in order to be applied to nonlinear models. Among them, the Ensemble Kalman Filter, EnKF, was proposed by Evensen (1994) and afterwards the Ensemble Kalman Smoother, EnKS, was introduced by Evensen and Leeuwen (1999). We now would like to present the EnKF and EnKS in some detail.

1.3.1 A different approach

If one wants to build a filter for nonlinear models, one must first consider how to compute the evolution of forecast errors through nonlinear integrations. Let us recall our dynamical model

$$\Psi_{k+1}^f = \Psi_k^a + f(\Psi_k^a) dt + d\beta_k. \quad (1.38)$$

In equation (1.38), we adopt a stochastic model, $d\beta_k$ is no longer an error between the “truth” and the forecast, but a representation of the inaccuracy of our model.

Just to present the theory, we will take shortly a continuous point of view. The equivalent system writes

$$d\Psi^t = f(\Psi^t) + d\beta. \quad (1.39)$$

We just recall that β is a Markov process and the covariance matrix of $d\beta$ depends on dt only.

Instead of computing just the evolution of the covariance matrix, we could try to compute the evolution of the distribution function of Ψ^f . If we succeed, it would always be possible to compute the covariance matrix from the distribution to perform the analysis step. So, what we are looking for is an equation describing the evolution of a distribution function.

Before presenting the theory, let us define our notations.

- For any continuous random variable \mathbf{X} , taking its value in \mathbb{R}^n , we call $g_{\mathbf{X}}(\mathbf{x})$ its distribution function,

$$\Pr(\mathbf{X} \in A) = \int_A g_{\mathbf{X}}(\mathbf{x}) d\mathbf{x}.$$

- For two continuous random variables \mathbf{X} and \mathbf{Y} , we call $g_{\mathbf{X}|\mathbf{Y}}(\mathbf{x}; \mathbf{y})$ the conditional density function of \mathbf{X} given \mathbf{Y} . Bayes' theorem then implies

$$g_{\mathbf{X}|\mathbf{Y}}(\mathbf{x}; \mathbf{y}) = \frac{g_{\mathbf{X},\mathbf{Y}}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y})}{g_{\mathbf{Y}}(\mathbf{y})}, \quad (1.40)$$

$$\text{with } g_{\mathbf{Y}}(\mathbf{y}) = \int_{\mathcal{D}_x} g_{\mathbf{X},\mathbf{Y}}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}) d\mathbf{x}. \quad (1.41)$$

The problem consists in deriving an equation which would describe the evolution of the density function. Firstly, we want to study the particular case of a dynamical system with no noise, and then we will give the general results when noise is added to the dynamical equation.

1.3.2 Kolmogorov's equations

Our hypotheses are as follows:

- $\Psi(t, \mathbf{x})$ is a solution of

$$d\Psi = f(\Psi)dt, \quad (1.42)$$

$$\Psi(0) = \mathbf{x}, \quad (1.43)$$

where f is a function from \mathbb{R}^n into \mathbb{R}^n , and we call f_i its i^{th} -component.

- $\mathbf{X}(t, \omega)$ is a random process whose definition is

$$\mathbf{X}(t, \omega) = \Psi(t, \mathbf{X}(0, \omega)).$$

It is then quite easy to verify that \mathbf{X} is a Markov process. This is just due to the uniqueness of the solution, once the initial conditions are provided.

- $g_{\mathbf{X}}(\mathbf{x}, t)$ is the density function of \mathbf{X} whose variations in time we want to characterize.

Jazwinsky (1970) has shown that the distribution function of \mathbf{X} was a solution of the equation,

$$\frac{\partial g_{\mathbf{X}}(\mathbf{x}, t)}{\partial t} + \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{\partial (g_{\mathbf{X}}(\mathbf{x}, t) f_i)}{\partial x_i} = 0. \quad (1.44)$$

This equation translates the conservation of “chances”. If at time t there is a certain amount of chances that \mathbf{X} takes its value in the ensemble A , at time $t + \delta t$, there is the same amount of chances that \mathbf{X} takes its values in $\Psi(\delta t, A)$. This is represented on figure 1.1. The paths build tubes which do not cross each other. This conservation comes from the fact that the paths of the random process \mathbf{X} cannot “disappear” or “appear” in the tube.

Figure 1.1: Conservation of the density function

We now assume our dynamical system writes

$$d\Psi = f(\Psi)dt + d\beta, \quad (1.45)$$

$$d\Psi(0) = \mathbf{x}. \quad (1.46)$$

We have already seen that β is a Markov process. Taking the same definition for \mathbf{X} , \mathbf{X} stays a Markov process. In this new system, noise's role can be compared to diffusion. If at time t , there is a certain amount of chances that \mathbf{X} takes its value

in the ensemble A , at time $t + \delta t$, the amount of chances that \mathbf{X} takes its values in $\Psi(\delta t, A)$ is diminished by the algebraic amount of chances that paths go “out” of the tube because of the noise. For an illustration of this principle, see figure 1.2.

Figure 1.2: Evolution of the paths when noise is added

The new equation describing the evolution of the distribution function becomes

$$\frac{\partial g_{\mathbf{x}}(x, t)}{\partial t} + \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{\partial (g_{\mathbf{x}}(x, t) f_i)}{\partial x_i} = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{i,j=1}^n Q_{i,j} \frac{\partial^2 g_{\mathbf{x}}(x, t)}{\partial x_i \partial x_j}, \quad (1.47)$$

where $Q_{i,j}$ is the covariance matrix of $d\boldsymbol{\beta}$.

Jazwinsky (1970) proves that it is theoretically possible to compute $g_{\mathbf{x}}(\mathbf{x}, t)$ from this equation in some particular simple cases. However, most of the time, it is not possible to compute analytically the density function. Evensen (1998) had then the idea of representing this density function with a finite set of elements. ‘‘Representing’’ a density function by an ensemble means that, according to the chosen precision, we construct an ensemble whose n first moments are the same as the ones of the distribution function. Then, instead of integrating the density function according to the equation (1.47), we integrate the members of the ensemble, according to the stochastic dynamical equation (1.45).

When we adopt this representation, we have to be aware of the hypotheses we make. Firstly, there is an error between the representation, a discrete ensemble, and the distribution function, which is continuous. This error depends on the number of members of the ensemble. Secondly, this error is going to evolve with time, since we integrate the members of the ensemble according to the dynamical equations, instead of integrating Kolmogorov’s equation. The assumption of the EnKF and the EnKS is that this error does not diverge during the integration step. However, the success of the application of the EnKF on various dynamical models lead us to think that this assumption is verified most of the time (see Evensen (1997), Evensen and Leeuwen (1996)).

This ensemble concept is very useful. Trying to compute a distribution function is a huge task, and only the two first moments are useful for the analysis step. On the contrary, integrating different members takes less time. Moreover, it is still possible to compute the forecast error covariance matrix which is needed for the analysis. Eventually, it is directly practical for implementation.

We have now explained the theory concerning the integration of the density function, and the representation of a density function by an ensemble. However, in order to be complete, we have to describe how to perform an analysis with density functions instead of quantities. The analysis step described in the Section 1.1 needs a forecast, an observation, and their relative error covariance matrix. We now would like to present what the analysis consists in, when we deal with density functions.

We call $g_{\Psi}(\mathbf{x})$ the distribution function of the forecast Ψ^f . Further, we introduce $g_{d|\Psi}(\mathbf{y}; \mathbf{x})$ the conditional distribution function of the observations given the forecasts. This means that we consider also the measurements as the realization of a random variable. This implies in the implementation, that when an observation is available, we have to generate an ensemble of observations, to represent the observations’ distribution function.

Once we have all this information, we can compute the density function of the analysed estimate. This density is in fact equal to the density function of the fore-

casts given the observations. By simply applying Bayes' theorem, we find

$$g_{\Psi|d}(\mathbf{x}; \mathbf{y}) = \frac{g_{\Psi}(\mathbf{x})g_{d|\Psi}(\mathbf{y}; \mathbf{x})}{\int_{\mathcal{D}} g_{\Psi}(\mathbf{x})g_{d|\Psi}(\mathbf{y}; \mathbf{x})d\mathbf{x}}. \quad (1.48)$$

This formula is what we should use if we wanted to perform the analysis corresponding to the study of distribution functions. However, this is not the approach chosen by the methodology of the EnKF. In the EnKF as well as in the EnKS, the analysis step is performed as in Section 1.1. When the dynamical system is linear, so that the distribution function $g_{\Psi}(\mathbf{x})$ stays Gaussian during the integration, the two approaches are equivalent. In fact, the approach with distribution functions computes the maximum likelihood estimate, whereas the analysis step described in Section 1.1 computes the minimum variance estimate and these two methods are equivalent with Gaussian distributions. However, if the distribution is strongly non Gaussian, problems arise. Further information about the consequences will be found in Evensen and Leeuwen (1999).

We will now present the extensive algorithm of the EnKF and the EnKS. For the sake of simplicity, we are going to return to a discrete point of view. The Ensemble filtering theory, described in a sequential manner is:

- $\Psi_i(t_k) \in \mathbb{R}^n$, is the i^{th} -vector state at time t_k of the whole ensemble.
- $P^f(t_k) \in \mathcal{M}_{n,n}(\mathbb{R})$, is the forecast error covariance matrix.
- $\mathbf{d}(t_k) \in \mathbb{R}^m$, is the observations vector at time t_k .
- $W^{-1} \in \mathcal{M}_{m,m}(\mathbb{R})$ is the observation error covariance matrix.

Note that we assume implicitly that the observation error covariance matrix does not vary with time.

1.3.3 The Ensemble Kalman Filter

At the very beginning, we generate an ensemble with n members which represents a Gaussian distribution centered around the value of the initial conditions and with a certain covariance matrix,

$$E(0) = \{\Psi_1(0), \Psi_2(0), \dots, \Psi_n(0)\}. \quad (1.49)$$

We then integrate each of the members according to the stochastic dynamical equation (1.38).

$$\Psi_j^f(t_{k+1}) = \Psi_j^a(t_k) + f(\Psi_j^a(t_k)) dt + d\beta_j(t_k), \quad (1.50)$$

with

$$\overline{\Psi^f(t_k)} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{j=1}^n \Psi_j^f(t_k), \quad (1.51)$$

$$P^f(t_k) = \frac{1}{n-1} \sum_{j=1}^n \left(\Psi_j^f(t_k) - \overline{\Psi^f(t_k)} \right)^T \left(\Psi_j^f(t_k) - \overline{\Psi^f(t_k)} \right). \quad (1.52)$$

Eventually, if observations are available, they may be used to update the ensemble. We need then to generate a Gaussian distributed ensemble of observations centered around the used observations $\mathbf{d}(t_k)$, and with a specified covariance matrix,

$$D(t_k) = \{\mathbf{d}_1(t_k), \mathbf{d}_2(t_k), \dots, \mathbf{d}_n(t_k)\}. \quad (1.53)$$

Afterwards, we just apply the general formula of Section 1.1 to each member of the ensemble.

$$\Psi_j^a(t_k) = \Psi_j^f(t_k) + K \left(\mathbf{d}_j(t_k) - H\Psi_j^f(t_k) \right). \quad (1.54)$$

The analysed estimate is the mean of the updated ensemble,

$$\overline{\Psi^a(t_k)} = \overline{\Psi^f(t_k)} + K \left(\mathbf{d}(t_k) - H\overline{\Psi^f(t_k)} \right). \quad (1.55)$$

Figure 1.3: Scheme of the EnKF algorithm.

Some simple results of the EnKF are now presented. They were obtained as follows. We considered a scalar state and in the dynamical stochastic equation (1.38), f is equal to 0. In Figure 1.4, it is clear that the variance of the ensemble strongly decreases after each analysis. We also note that the analysed states are almost equal to the observations. This is due to a simple fact, the variance for the observation is much smaller than the variance for the ensemble when the analysis is performed.

Figure 1.4: Results of the EnKF for a simple model with f equal to 0.

1.3.4 The Ensemble Kalman Smoother

The EnKS is an improvement of the EnKF because it suppresses these strong variations when data assimilation is performed. The theory is developed by Evensen and Leeuwen (1999), and we present the methodology.

We call $\Phi_j^f(t_k)$ the total path of the j^{th} member of the ensemble from time 0 to time t_k ,

$$\Phi_j^f(t_k) = (\Psi_j^a(0), \Psi_j^a(t_1), \dots, \Psi_j^a(t_{k-1}), \Psi_j^f(t_k))^T. \quad (1.56)$$

Nevertheless, the measurement matrix H keeps the same definition as in the EnKF because the potential data assimilation uses only the last measurement. Thus,

$$\mathbf{d}(t_k) = H\Psi^t(t_k) + \varepsilon \quad (1.57)$$

$$\Psi(t_k) = L_k\Phi(t_k). \quad (1.58)$$

where L_k is a linear operator, from \mathbb{R}^{nk} into \mathbb{R}^n , whose result is a vector equal to the last n components of its argument. If at time t_k observations are available, the EnKF updates only the last point of the path, $\Psi_j^f(t_k)$, whereas the EnKS updates

the whole path $\Phi_j^f(t_k)$. This guaranties the smoothness of the solution,

$$\overline{\Phi^f(t_k)} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{j=1}^n \Phi_j^f(t_k), \quad (1.59)$$

$$R^f(t_k) = \frac{1}{n-1} \sum_{j=1}^n \left(\Phi_j^f(t_k) - \overline{\Phi^f(t_k)} \right)^T \left(\Phi_j^f(t_k) - \overline{\Phi^f(t_k)} \right), \quad (1.60)$$

$$P^f(t_k) = L_k R^f(t_k) L_k^T. \quad (1.61)$$

where $R^f(t_k)$ is the path error covariance matrix. Afterwards, the analysis step is the same as in Subsection 1.1.2. We write the penalty function,

$$\mathcal{J}[\Phi] = (\Phi^f - \Phi)^T (P^f)^{-1} (\Phi^f - \Phi) + (\mathbf{d} - H\Psi)^T W (\mathbf{d} - H\Psi), \quad (1.62)$$

$$\mathcal{J}[\Phi] = (\Phi^f - \Phi)^T (P^f)^{-1} (\Phi^f - \Phi) + (\mathbf{d} - HL_k\Phi)^T W (\mathbf{d} - HL_k\Phi), \quad (1.63)$$

where Φ^f stands for any path $\Phi_j^f(t_k)$ of the ensemble, Ψ^f for $\Psi_j^f(t_k)$, and \mathbf{d} for $\mathbf{d}_j(t_k)$. Then, we just have to apply to each member of the ensemble the results of the variance minimizing method (1.25) and (1.27), replacing H by HL_k .

$$\Phi_j^a(t_k) = \Phi_j^f(t_k) + K \left(\mathbf{d}_j(t_k) - HL_k\Phi_j^f(t_k) \right), \quad (1.64)$$

$$K = R^f(t_k) (HL_k)^T (W^{-1} + HL_k R^f(t_k) (HL_k)^T)^{-1}. \quad (1.65)$$

Simplifying these two equations gives,

$$\Phi_j^a(t_k) = \Phi_j^f(t_k) + K \left(\mathbf{d}_j(t_k) - H\Psi_j^f(t_k) \right), \quad (1.66)$$

$$K = R^f(t_k) L_k^T H^T (W^{-1} + H P^f(t_k) H^T)^{-1}. \quad (1.67)$$

This result can be formulated another way, by using the representers approach,

$$\Phi_j^a(t_k) = \Phi_j^f(t_k) + r^T \mathbf{b}_j(t_k), \quad (1.68)$$

$$\mathbf{b}_j(t_k) = (W^{-1} + H P^f(t_k) H^T)^{-1} \left(\mathbf{d}_j(t_k) - H\Psi_j^f(t_k) \right), \quad (1.69)$$

$$r = HL_k R^f(t_k). \quad (1.70)$$

Eventually, the analysed estimate is the mean of the updated ensemble of paths.

$$\overline{\Phi^a(t_k)} = \overline{\Phi^f(t_k)} + K \left(\mathbf{d}(t_k) - H\overline{\Psi^f(t_k)} \right). \quad (1.71)$$

For large time scale, the EnKS may be heavy to compute, if at each analysis step the whole path is updated. Moreover, as time increases, the update of a state at a fixed time decreases. For instance, if at time t_{50} the update of the first component of the state vector at time t_{30} is equal to u ,

$$\left[K \left(\mathbf{d}(t_{50}) - H\overline{\Psi^f(t_{50})} \right) \right]_{29n+1} = u, \quad (1.72)$$

Figure 1.5: Scheme of the EnKS algorithm.

the update of the same quantity at time t_{70} will be much inferior to u . Therefore, it can be a good idea to use a “lagged” EnKS, in order to reduce the computation time. The formulation of this “lagged” smoother is exactly the same as the EnKS except that Φ is defined as

$$\Phi_j^f(t_k) = (\Psi_j^a(t_{k-lag+1}), \Psi_j^a(t_{k-lag+2}), \dots, \Psi_j^a(t_{k-1}), \Psi_j^f(t_k))^T, \quad (1.73)$$

so that $\Phi_j^f(t_k)$ has always the same dimension. lag is chosen arbitrarily at the very beginning, according to the number of steps backward we want to update.

1.3.5 The Particle Filter

The Particle Filter’s theory is an interesting alternative to the EnKF, but it needs further practical studies in order to be applied to models with numerous variables. We now would like to present briefly the scheme of the Particle Filter, because its methodology uses the conditional distribution function of the forecast given the observations (1.48). At the initialization, the Particle Filter generates an ensemble of n members as the EnKF. However, the EnKF considers this ensemble as a representation of the initial distribution function, whereas the Particle Filter considers it as

Figure 1.6: Results of the EnKS.

n values with a probability of $1/n$ to occur. Therefore, the Particle Filter links each member of the initial ensemble with a weight which represents its probability to be realized.

Both the EnKF and the Particle Filter have the same integration step, all the members are integrated forward in time according to the sequential stochastic dynamical equation (1.38). The analysis step is the point where these methodologies differ. While the EnKF performs the variance minimizing method on each of its member, the Particle Filter uses the observations' distribution function in order to upgrade the weights of the members, i.e. their probability to occur.

The major negative point of the Particle Filter is that it needs much more members than the Ensemble Filters, in order to represent correctly the distribution function and is therefore unapplicable to dynamical problems where the phase space's dimension is too large.

Chapter 2

Marine ecosystems modeling

It is quite well-known that the ocean is strongly coupled with the atmosphere. However, to a beginner, the coupling between marine biota and the atmosphere seems less evident, although it is quite important. For instance, the marine biota play an important role in the carbon cycle, mainly through photosynthesis.

Therefore, a better understanding of general dynamical systems, such as the carbon cycle, implies a better knowledge of marine ecosystems. Improvements come of course from efforts in modelling the reality as closely as possible. However, other ways should not be neglected -data assimilation methods can lead to strong ameliorations in different fields. Firstly, it allows to compute better estimates of the studied variables of the biological models. Secondly, it is a very promising way of estimating poorly known parameters which are numerous in biological models and can have a great impact concerning the sensitivity of these models (see Fasham and Evans (1995), Harmon and Challenor (1996), and Evensen et al. (1998)).

In this report, we focus on two marine ecosystems models. The first one is fairly simple, with three compartments (nutrients, phytoplankton, herbivorous zooplankton), and was presented by Evans and Parslow (1985), the second one is a bit more complex since it contains seven compartments, and was described by Fasham et al. (1990).

Both of these models focus on the nitrate cycles and not on the carbon cycle. This is due to a simple fact. In order to study the carbon cycle, we have to model the living cycle of marine biota. Nevertheless, nitrates and not carbon are the limiting factor of growth of the main compartment, phytoplankton. For this reason the nitrate cycle is modelled rather than the carbon cycle. Once the biological interactions between the different compartments have been set, the carbon cycle can be studied.

In both models, the dynamics of the mixed layer is very important -the mixed layer is the upper inhomogeneous layer of the ocean which is continuously turbulent because of the wind's activity. In fact, nutrients (or nitrates) are assumed to have a very high concentration below the mixed layer. Therefore, at the end of the winter, when the mixed layer deepens, the concentration of nitrates in the mixed layer increases, building the environmental conditions for the next spring bloom.

Our models are rather coarse concerning the euphotic zone. We did not make an attempt to separate the euphotic zone from the non-euphotic zone (the euphotic zone is the upper layer, which keeps 90 percent of the sun energy). Therefore, we

did not introduce regeneration of the compartments below the euphotic zone, and we solved the biological equations on the whole depth.

Both of the models have been implemented on the same numerical grid. The total depth is 200 meters, and there are 20 nodes in the vertical direction. Concerning the time scale, we run both of them over 5 years in order to reach a stable cycle, and then we study them over one year.

2.1 The three-compartment model

Evans and Parslow (1985) developed a fairly simple model in order to study the annual cycle of the marine ecosystem. The dynamical system is supposed to possess an attractive period where most of the paths will converge independently from the initial conditions.

Moreover, Evans and Parslow (1985) represented the effect of the mixed layer by adding an asymmetrical diffusion term averaged on the total mixed layer. We replaced this term by a diffusion term and studied the model evolving with 1-dimensional physical dynamics.

We adopt the following notations for the state variables :

- N stands for nutrients.
- P stands for phytoplankton.
- H stands for herbivores.

2.1.1 Equation for phytoplankton

Phytoplankton's concentration is modelled as

$$\frac{\partial P}{\partial t} = \left(\frac{JN}{j+N} - r \right) P - \frac{c(P - P_0)H}{k + P - P_0} + \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \left(K(z, M) \frac{\partial P}{\partial z} \right). \quad (2.1)$$

The first term in equation (2.1) represents the photosynthetic activity of phytoplankton, which is limited by nutrients' concentration where j is the uptake half saturation parameter, r , the plant metabolic loss and J the photosynthetic rate of phytoplankton making the link between some forcing fields and the model (its formulation is given at the end of Section 2.1).

The second term of equation (2.1) represents the loss due to herbivores grazing on phytoplankton and is detailed after the presentation of the zooplankton's equation (2.2).

K is the diffusion coefficient and we detail its formulation in the subsection 2.1.4.

2.1.2 Equation for herbivores

Zooplankton's equation is modelled as

$$\frac{\partial H}{\partial t} = \frac{fc(P - P_0)H}{k + P - P_0} - gH + \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \left(K(z, M) \frac{\partial H}{\partial z} \right). \quad (2.2)$$

In equation (2.2), the first term represents the grazing of herbivores on phytoplankton. c is the maximum grazing rate, and f is the grazing efficiency. P_0 is the grazing threshold, whereas k is the grazing half saturation.

The second term is the loss of herbivores due to mortality and g is the loss to carnivores rate. In this model, it is then assumed that herbivores concentration decreases only because of higher predators which are not modelled.

2.1.3 Equation for nutrients

Nutrients' concentration is modelled as

$$\frac{\partial N}{\partial t} = - \left(\frac{JN}{j + N} - r \right) P + \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \left(K(z, M) \frac{\partial N}{\partial z} \right). \quad (2.3)$$

The first term of equation (2.3) is the loss of nutrients due to phytoplankton grazing. We assume that the concentration of nutrients below the mixed layer is constant, so that nutrients do not disappear totally. This condition is a forcing field in this model, but could be removed with a modelization of nutrients' regeneration.

2.1.4 Equation for the diffusion term

We followed Eknes and Evensen (1999) in their formulation of the diffusion term K

$$K(z, M) = K_b + \frac{(K_0 - K_b) (\arctan(\gamma(M - z)) - \arctan(\gamma(M - D)))}{\arctan(\gamma M) - \arctan(\gamma(M - D))}. \quad (2.4)$$

Here, K_b is the value of the diffusion coefficient at the bottom, and K_0 at the surface, γ is the thermocline sharpness, (the bigger γ is, the quicker the decreasing of K at the mixed layer depth, see Figures 2.1 and 2.2) and D is the total depth while M is the depth of the mixed layer.

Figure 2.1: Diffusion coefficient with a thermocline sharpness equal to 0.1.

Figure 2.2: Diffusion coefficient with a thermocline sharpness equal to 0.5

2.1.5 Forcing fields and parameters

We would like to sum up the different forcing fields of this model.

- N_0 is the concentration of the nutrients below the mixed layer. We followed Evans and Parslow (1985) and set it equal to 10 mM/m^3 .
- Latitude sets a second forcing field, solar radiation, which is involved in the computation of J . We studied this model at 47 degrees north.

Phytoplankton parameters	Symbol	Value	Units
Uptake half saturation	j	0.5	$m \text{ mol m}^{-3}$
Plant metabolic loss	r	0.07	d^{-1}
Zooplankton parameters			
Grazing threshold	P_0	0.1	$m \text{ mol m}^{-3}$
Grazing half saturation	k	1.0	$m \text{ mol m}^{-3}$
Maximum grazing rate	c	1.0	d^{-1}
Grazing efficiency	f	0.5	
Loss to carnivores	g	0.07	d^{-1}
Diffusion parameters			
	K_0	0.01	$\text{m}^2 \text{d}^{-1}$
	K_b	0.0001	$\text{m}^2 \text{d}^{-1}$

Table 2.1: The numerical value and units of the parameters used in the 3 compartment-ecosystem model.

The whole computation of J will now be presented. It is directly taken from Evans and Parslow (1985). Similarly to Evans and Parslow (1985), the light limited growth rate is averaged over a day, since we do not attempt to model precisely a very short

time. However, instead of averaging this rate over the total depth of the mixed layer, we compute it at the depth where it is needed.

Following Evans and Parslow (1985), we introduce this function, which is the light limited growth rate at a certain time and depth,

$$G = \frac{V_p \alpha I}{\sqrt{V_p^2 + (\alpha I)^2}}. \quad (2.5)$$

Here, I is the local light level just below the surface of the water which is photosynthetically active, V_p is the maximum photosynthetic rate, and α is the initial slope in the P/I curve,

$$\alpha = \frac{\partial P}{\partial I}(I = 0). \quad (2.6)$$

In equation (2.5), I is a function depending on the time. We assume its variation is triangular.

$$I = \frac{t}{\tau} \exp(-k_w z) I_{\text{noon}}, \quad (2.7)$$

$$\text{if } t < \tau,$$

$$I(\tau - t) = I(\tau + t), \quad (2.8)$$

$$t \in [0; \tau],$$

where τ is half of the daylength, t is equal to 0 at sunrise and k_w is the light attenuation coefficient due to water, and I_{noon} is the light level below the surface at noon which is photosynthetically active (it depends on the cloudiness, c_1 , on the transmission losses due to clouds, c_2 , on the rate of photosynthetically active radiation, par).

Astronomic formulae allow us to compute τ , half of the daylength, and J_0 , the total light at the top of the atmosphere,

$$\delta = -0.406 \cos(2\pi T), \quad (2.9)$$

$$\tau = \frac{1}{2} \arccos(-\tan(\delta) \tan(\phi)), \quad (2.10)$$

$$I_{\text{noon}}^{\text{top}} = \frac{R}{\pi \tau} (\sin(\delta) \sin(\phi) \tau + \cos(\delta) \cos(\phi) \sin(\tau)), \quad (2.11)$$

$$I_{\text{noon}} = c_1 c_2 par I_{\text{noon}}^{\text{top}}, \quad (2.12)$$

where δ is the declination, T is the time of the year, R is the solar constant and ϕ is the latitude, our second forcing field.

It is now possible to express the light limited growth rate (2.5) as a function of time and depth only. We just have to average it over a daylength 2τ ,

$$\begin{aligned} J(z, T, \phi) &= 2 \int_0^\tau G(z, T, \phi, t) dt, \\ &= 2 V_p^2 \frac{\tau}{\alpha I_{\text{noon}}} \left(\sqrt{1 + \frac{(\alpha I_{\text{noon}})^2}{V_p^2} \exp(-2kz)} - 1 \right). \end{aligned} \quad (2.13)$$

Parameters	Symbol	Value	Units
Maximum photosynthetic rate	V_p	2	d^{-1}
Low light photosynthetic slope	α	0.04	$\text{m}^2(\text{Wd})^{-1}$
Light attenuation by water	k	0.1	m^{-1}
Solar constant	R	1365	W/m^2
PAR	par	0.375	
Cloud cover	c_1	0.9	
Transmission losses	c_2	0.7	

Table 2.2: The numerical value and units of the parameters used to compute the light limited growth rate.

2.2 The seven-compartment model

This model was originally developed in 1990 to study the annual cycle of nitrogen at Station ‘S’ near Bermuda ($32^\circ 10' \text{N}$; $64^\circ 30' \text{W}$). It was afterwards slightly adjusted in 1993 in order to fit to observations at Ocean Weather Station ‘India’ (59° ; 10°). We chose the last version for our experiments. The dynamical equations will now be presented with their general meaning and we adopt the following notations for the state variables:

- P stands for phytoplankton.
- Z stands for herbivorous zooplankton.
- B stands for bacteria.
- N_n stands for nitrate nitrogen.
- N_a stands for ammonium.
- N_d stands for dissolved organic nitrogen.
- D stands for detritus.

2.2.1 Equation for phytoplankton

Phytoplankton’s concentration is modelled as

$$\frac{\partial P}{\partial t} = (1 - \gamma)J \left(\tilde{N}_n + \tilde{N}_a \right) P - G_1 - \frac{\mu_1 P^2}{k_5 + P} + \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \left(K(z, M) \frac{\partial P}{\partial z} \right), \quad (2.14)$$

where J is the light limited growth rate of the phytoplankton. This factor play an important role in the cycle of the model, because it directly limits the ability of the phytoplankton to grow. The computation of J is slightly different from the previous computation in Section 2.1, because it introduces another forcing field, the

sea surface temperature. We will detail how to compute J at the end of Section 2.2. \tilde{N}_n and \tilde{N}_a are nondimensional nutrient limiting factors.

$$\tilde{N}_n = \frac{N_n e^{-\psi N_a}}{k_1 + N_n}, \quad (2.15)$$

$$\tilde{N}_a = \frac{N_a}{k_2 + N_a}, \quad (2.16)$$

where ψ transcribes the preference of phytoplankton to feed on ammonium rather than on nitrate. G_1 is the loss of phytoplankton due to zooplankton grazing. Eventually, $\mu_1 P^2 / (k_5 + P)$ is the loss of phytoplankton due to mortality.

To sum up this equation, phytoplankton is the only organism able to use the solar energy, and for this reason, this compartment is at the beginning of the biological pump. Phytoplankton's concentration can decrease, either because of zooplankton feeding or because of simple mortality.

2.2.2 Equation for zooplankton

Zooplankton's concentration is modelled as

$$\frac{\partial Z}{\partial t} = \beta_1 G_1 + \beta_2 G_2 + \beta_3 G_3 - \frac{\mu_2 Z^2}{k_6 + Z} + \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \left(K(z, M) \frac{\partial Z}{\partial z} \right), \quad (2.17)$$

where G_1 , G_2 , and G_3 are the grazing rates of zooplankton on phytoplankton, bacteria and detritus. The β quantities describe the efficiency of zooplankton to assimilate its food.

The fourth term of equation (2.17) represents the decreasing of zooplankton's concentration due to excretions or to mortality. We do not differentiate the two causes since both of them produce either ammonium or dissolved organic nitrogen. However, only a fraction of this quantity is turned into ammonium or dissolved organic nitrogen. The remaining loss is mainly due to higher predators (see Fasham (1992) and Drange (1996)) and is considered as fast sinking materials.

In the following grazing function, I represents P , B , or D , and i takes the value 1, 2, or 3,

$$G_i = g Z p_i \frac{I^2}{k_3(p_1 P + p_2 B + p_3 D) + p_1 P^2 + p_2 B^2 + p_3 D^2}, \quad (2.18)$$

where g is the maximum ingestion rate and p_1 , p_2 , p_3 are measures of the zooplankton preferences for phytoplankton, bacteria, and detritus.

2.2.3 Equation for bacteria

Bacteria's concentration is modelled as

$$\frac{\partial B}{\partial t} = U_1 + U_2 - \mu_3 B - G_2 + \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \left(K(z, M) \frac{\partial B}{\partial z} \right). \quad (2.19)$$

In equation 2.19, U_1 is the dissolved organic nitrogen uptake, and U_2 is the ammonium uptake. The formulation of these quantities comes from consideration about the C/N ratios (C for carbon and N for nitrate),

$$S = \text{Min}(N_a, \eta N_d), \quad (2.20)$$

$$U_1 = \frac{V_b BS}{K_4 + S(1 + \eta)}, \quad (2.21)$$

$$U_2 = \eta U_1, \quad (2.22)$$

where η is the ratio between ammonium uptake and dissolved organic nitrogen uptake. We consider it as a constant parameter of the model. V_b is the maximum bacterial uptake rate. The third term of equation (2.19) represents bacterial excrements, which are turned into ammonium. Therefore, the main role of bacteria in the model is to transform the ingested dissolved organic nitrogen into ammonium

2.2.4 Equation for nitrate nitrogen

Nitrogen's concentration is modelled as

$$\frac{\partial N_n}{\partial t} = -J \frac{N_n e^{-\psi N_a}}{k_1 + N_n} + \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \left(K(z, M) \frac{\partial N_n}{\partial z} \right), \quad (2.23)$$

In this model, nitrate disappear because of phytoplankton grazing. If we had made a distinction between the euphotic zone and the non-euphotic zone, we could introduce the nitrate regeneration in the non euphotic zone. However, we decided to keep a simple model, and the regeneration was therefore replaced by a boundary condition on nitrate at the bottom of the model domain.

2.2.5 Equation for ammonium

Ammonium's concentration is modelled as

$$\frac{\partial N_a}{\partial t} = -J \frac{N_a}{k_2 + N_a} - U_2 + \mu_3 B + \frac{\varepsilon \mu_2 Z^2}{k_6 + Z} + \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \left(K(z, M) \frac{\partial N_a}{\partial z} \right). \quad (2.24)$$

As for nitrate, ammonium is regenerated below the euphotic zone. Because we did not introduce regeneration equations, we set a boundary condition on ammonium at the bottom of the sea. In this way, we did not follow the assumption of Fasham (1992) who took a concentration of ammonium equal to zero below the mixed layer.

2.2.6 Equation for dissolved organic nitrogen

Dissolved organic nitrogen's concentration is modelled as

$$\frac{\partial N_d}{\partial t} = \gamma J(t, M) \left(\tilde{N}_n + \tilde{N}_a \right) P + \mu_4 D + \frac{\delta \mu_2 Z^2}{k_6 + Z} - U_1 + \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \left(K(z, M) \frac{\partial N_d}{\partial z} \right). \quad (2.25)$$

The first term of equation (2.25) is the production of dissolved organic nitrogen through phytoplankton exudation, and the second term represents the detrital breakdown into dissolved organic nitrogen.

2.2.7 Equation for detritus

Detritus' concentration is modelled as

$$\frac{\partial D}{\partial t} = \sum_{i=1}^3 (1 - \beta_i) G_i - G_3 - \mu_4 D + \frac{\mu_1 P^2}{k_5 + P} + \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \left(K(z, M) \frac{\partial D}{\partial z} \right) + w \frac{\partial D}{\partial z}. \quad (2.26)$$

The first term of equation 2.26 is the food that zooplankton is unable to assimilate and which is therefore turned into detritus. The last term of equation 2.26 represents the detritus sinking.

2.2.8 Forcing fields and parameters

Compared to the 3-compartment model, we have 4 forcing fields.

- The bottom of the sea is considered to be a source of ammonium and nitrates, in order to replace the equations of regeneration. We chose 2 mmol m^{-3} for the nitrate concentration, and 0.5 mmol m^{-3} for the ammonium concentration at the bottom.
- Latitude sets a third forcing field, solar radiation, which is involved in the computation of J . As this model was developed firstly for observations at the Bermuda station "S", we set the latitude equal to 32 degrees north.
- Eventually, the last forcing comes from the sea-surface temperature. As we did not have real sea surface temperatures, we modelled them by linearizing observations from Drange (1996).

We now would like to explain how we computed J , the light limited growth rate. We took exactly the same formula as in section 2.1, but we introduce the forcing of the sea surface temperature by using Eppley's formula to compute the maximum growth rate,

$$V_p = 0.6(1.066)^{T/1^\circ\text{C}}. \quad (2.27)$$

Phytoplankton parameters	Symbol	Value	Units
DON exudation fraction	γ	0.05	—
Maximum specific mortality rate	μ_1	0.05	d^{-1}
Half-saturation const. for nitrate	k_1	0.5	$m \text{ mol m}^{-3}$
Half-saturation const. for ammonium	k_2	0.5	$m \text{ mol m}^{-3}$
Half-saturation const. for mortality	k_5	0.2	$m \text{ mol m}^{-3}$
Ammonium inhibition parameter	ψ	1.5	$\text{m}^3 m \text{ mol}^{-1}$
Initial slope of P-I curve	α	0.025	$\text{m}^2 \text{ W}^{-1} \text{ d}^{-1}$
Light attenuation due to water	k_w	0.04	m^{-1}
Light attenuation due to phytoplankton	k_c	0.03	$\text{m}^2 m \text{ mol}^{-1}$
Photosynthetically active radiation	par	0.43	—
Zooplankton parameters			
Assimilation efficiency w.r.t. phytoplankton	β_1	0.75	—
Assimilation efficiency w.r.t. bacteria	β_2	0.75	—
Assimilation efficiency w.r.t. detritus	β_3	0.75	—
Maximum loss rate	μ_2	0.3	d^{-1}
Maximum ingestion rate	g	1.0	d^{-1}
Half-saturation for ingestion	k_3	1.0	$m \text{ mol m}^{-3}$
Half-saturation for losses	k_6	0.2	$m \text{ mol m}^{-3}$
Relative preference for phytoplankton	p_1	0.5	—
Relative preference for bacteria	p_2	0.25	—
Relative preference for detritus	p_3	0.25	—
Bacteria parameters			
Specific excretion rate	μ_3	0.05	d^{-1}
Maximum uptake (growth) rate	V_b	2.0	d^{-1}
Half-saturation rate for uptake	k_4	0.5	$m \text{ mol m}^{-3}$
Ammonium/don uptake ratio	η	0.6	—
DON, ammonium and detritus			
Fraction of zoop. losses going to DON	δ	0.2	—
Fraction of zoop. losses going to ammonium	ε	0.7	—
Breakdown rate	μ_4	0.05	d^{-1}
Sinking velocity	w	1.0	m d^{-1}

Table 2.3: The numerical value and units of the parameters used in the 7-compartment ecosystem model.

Chapter 3

Results of the twin experiments

The EnKF and EnKS exposed in the first chapter will now be applied in a twin experiment using the ecosystem models presented in the second chapter.

3.1 What is a twin experiment?

Data assimilation methods have to be tested before being confronted with real observations. A twin experiment consists in a test where we simulate the observations according to the dynamical model. This test has two purposes; validating the methodology and characterizing its behaviour. Concerning the first point, it is useless to try to apply data assimilation methods with real observations if they do not work in a perfect world where observations are consistent with model dynamics. Secondly, by studying the methodology with “perfect” data, we are able to point out any significant behaviour, such as the introduction of a bias, which is only due to the methodology. Eventually, the twin experiment allows to study the influence of the chosen initial variances on the results.

The steps in the twin experiment are as follows:

- Firstly, we run the model during 5 years of spin up. This is to reach a stable cycle, independently from the initial conditions. After this spin up, we have correct initial conditions for the different state variables. These initial conditions serve two purposes.

Firstly, they are used to generate over a year a reference solution which is taken to be the “truth”. In order to build the reference solution, we add after each integration step some Gaussian random quantity, which is our representation of the inaccuracy of the model. This random quantity is drawn out of a Gaussian variable whose mean is equal to 0 and whose variance is chosen to be equal to var_{dyn} .

Secondly, these initial conditions are used to compute our initial “best guess” of the system.

- The second step consists in generating the initial ensemble. We assume that the distribution function for the initial conditions is Gaussian and therefore,

Parameters	Symbol	Value for N	Value for P	Value for H
Dynamical variance	var_{dyn}	0.00001	0.00001	0.00001
Initial variance	var_{ini}	0.000625	0.0001	0.0001
Measurement variance	var_{meas}	0.000625	0.0001	0.0001

Table 3.1: The numerical value of the variances used in the 3-compartment model.

we take our initial “best guess” and add to it a Gaussian random vector whose mean is equal to 0 and whose variance is chosen to be equal to var_{ini} .

- Thirdly, we simulate our observations by taking the reference solution and adding to it a random quantity. This quantity is drawn out of a Gaussian distribution whose mean is equal to 0 and whose variance is equal to var_{meas} . Concerning the 7-compartment model, we simulated observations which were in a interval centered around the reference solution and whose radius was equal to var_{meas} . For both of the models, we chose to simulate 40 observations regularly spaced over a year.
- Eventually, we integrate each member of the ensemble, adding after each integration step a Gaussian random vector with mean equal to 0 and variance equal to var_{dyn} , and, whenever observations are available, we perform data assimilation. For this purpose, we generate an ensemble of observations by adding to the chosen observation a Gaussian random vector with mean equal to 0 and variance equal to var_{meas} . Our aim is here to compare the different results between the Ensemble Kalman Filter and the Ensemble Kalman Smoother.

3.2 Results of the three-compartment model

With the 3-compartment model, we use an ensemble of 100 members. Data assimilation was performed observing only the concentration of phytoplankton on the total depth. Table 3.1 sums up the variances we chose for our implementation.

3.2.1 Reference solution and climatology

Figure 3.1 shows the reference solution and Figure 3.2 presents the results of the climatology. The climatology experiment consists in integrating all the members of the ensemble, without performing data assimilation. In fact, this experiment shows the unstable behaviour of the 3-compartment model. For very close initial conditions, the results after an integration over a year are sensibly different. The climatology is also a way to check the results of the EnKF and the EnKS.

Figure 3.1 can be commented in the light of the dynamical equations. During the winter, the mixed layer deepens and entrains lots of nutrients, so that the nutrient concentration in the mixed layer increases. This is noticeable on the top picture of Figure 3.1 during the first hundred days and at the end of the year. This builds

the environmental conditions for the spring bloom of phytoplankton, which begins after 100 days. Phytoplankton's bloom is then followed by herbivores' bloom. As phytoplankton grazes on nutrients, the concentration of nutrients decreases during the bloom and this is the end of the cycle.

3.2.2 Ensemble Filters

Figure 3.3 exposes the results of the Ensemble Kalman Filter. We have already noticed on the simple example of Figure 1.4 the important variations when the Ensemble Kalman Filter is applied. As we observe the concentration of phytoplankton, the effects of data assimilation are really obvious on the middle picture representing the phytoplankton estimate and, especially during the spring bloom. Those effects are also noticeable on the bottom picture, which represents the herbivores estimate. However, the nutrients estimate does not show any strong variation at all. Looking back at the dynamical equations 2.1 of the 3-compartment model, we know there is a direct correlation between nutrients and phytoplankton. If the effects of the Ensemble Kalman Filter are not noticeable, it might be because the dynamical variance for nutrients is quite low, so that the ensemble does not spread much around the value of nutrients' concentration.

Figure 3.4 presents the results of the Ensemble Kalman Smoother. Concerning the phytoplankton and herbivores estimate, the improvement is obvious : during the spring bloom, all the strong variations have been removed.

The difference between the Ensemble Kalman Filter and Smoother can be studied on Figure 3.5. "MSE" stands for Mean Square Error, and is computed by summing all the variances over the whole depth and taking the root square of it. On the graphs representing the MSE for phytoplankton and herbivores, the amelioration of the smoother is clear. Figure 3.5 allows also to notice that the amelioration of the Ensemble Kalman Smoother decreases with time. This is due to the simple fact that estimations at the beginning benefit from all the corrections coming from later observations.

Eventually we would like to draw a small conclusion. The three compartment model is a very good example illustrating a simple remark. Even if the variances of the measurements are larger than the dynamical variances, which means that we trust the model more than the observations, data assimilation is really efficient because of the unstability of the equations during the spring bloom.

3.3 Results of the seven-compartment model

With the 7-compartment model, we used an ensemble of 200 members. As our study focused on this model, we present more results concerning data assimilation. Firstly, we simulated observations which are available in the reality, the concentration of phytoplankton at the surface and the profile over the total depth of nitrates nitrogen concentration. Concerning the variance, we took the same notations as in Section 3.2.

We perform all our experiments with a simple idea in mind, i.e. checking that assimilating sea surface observations of phytoplankton's concentration is efficient.

Figure 3.1: “Reference” solution with the 3-compartment model.

Figure 3.2: climatology experiment with the 3-compartment model.

Figure 3.3: Ensemble Kalman Filter applied to the 3-compartment model, observing phytoplankton's concentration over the whole depth.

Figure 3.4: Ensemble Kalman Smoother applied to the 3-compartment model, observing phytoplankton's concentration over the whole depth.

Figure 3.5: Mean Square Errors of the EnKF and the EnKS applied to the 3-compartment model, observing phytoplankton's concentration over the whole depth.

We focus on these data especially, because they are provided quite easily by satellites. In fact, pictures taken with satellites allow to measure the concentration of chlorophyll at the sea surface, and this quantity is directly linked to phytoplankton's concentration. In order to analyse the results of assimilating only sea surface observations of phytoplankton, we compare them to assimilating other quantities such as observations of phytoplankton or nitrate over the whole depth. Moreover, we focus on the same variables as in the 3-compartment model, because others are not as affected by the difference in the data assimilation methods. This is just because their correlation with the observed variables is quite low.

3.3.1 Reference solution and climatology

We first present the results of the reference solution and the climatology experiment, which has already been described in Subsection 3.2.1. On Figure 3.6, the reference solution seems to be more noisy compared to the 3-compartment model; this is because the characteristic concentrations are lower, so that the stochastic behaviour is more apparent.

In the opposite of the 3-compartment model, the 7-compartment model is very stable, even during the spring bloom. This is immediately noticeable on Figure 3.7 which, except for the noise, is rather similar to the reference solution. Note that there is no noise in the climatology because it is the mean of the ensemble.

3.3.2 Assimilating phytoplankton at the surface only

We present now the results of the EnKF and the EnKS, when data assimilation is performed with observations of phytoplankton's concentration only at the surface.

Figure 3.8 presents the results of the EnKF. The EnKF updates are not as noticeable as in the 3-compartment model. Only a close look at the estimate of the phytoplankton's concentration help us to identify the EnKF. This has two causes. Firstly, the 7-compartment model is more stable, secondly, the control for the upgrade decreases with depth, so that nutrients at the bottom of the sea are less affected by the EnKF for instance.

Figure 3.9 presents the results of the EnKS. At first sight, the results are fairly the same as for the EnKF. However, looking at the zooplankton's concentration, we notice that the EnKS detects a larger concentration at around 175 days, which is not shown by the EnKF, although it is present in the reference solution. Furthermore, as expected, quick variations of phytoplankton's estimate have been removed by the EnKS.

Figures 3.10 and 3.11 plot the standard deviation of the ensemble when using the EnKF and the EnKS respectively. We now would like to explain the spatial structure of the standard deviation. At the bottom of the model domain, the standard deviation is very low because of the strong boundary conditions on all the variables. In fact, in our twin experiment, we considered the boundary conditions as weak constraints by adding to the imposed boundary value a gaussian noise with mean equal to 0. Nevertheless, it seems that the variance of this gaussian noise is too small, since the stochastic boundary condition still prevents the ensemble from spreading

Figure 3.6: Reference solution of the 7-compartment model.

Figure 3.7: Climatology results of the 7-compartment model.

Figure 3.8: EnKF applied to the 7-compartment model, observing phytoplankton's concentration at the surface only.

Figure 3.9: EnKS applied to the 7-compartment model, observing phytoplankton's concentration at the surface only.

at the bottom of our model domain..

On the top picture of Figure 3.10, the EnKF shows how rapidly the increase of the standard deviation at the surface propagates with the depth. It means that the surface is very correlated to the mid-depth. This can be verified on the top picture for Figure 3.11. In fact, if surface phytoplankton's concentration is very correlated with mid-depth phytoplankton's concentration, we would expect to have a good improvement due to the use of the EnKS on the first 100 meters, and this is exactly what we get. Concerning the 100 last meters, results of the EnKF and EnKS are very similar. From this, we can draw as a conclusion that sea surface observations of phytoplankton's concentration assimilated with the EnKS allow to control the first 100 meters. Even if we did not test it, we are of the opinion that the results would be similar with a deeper sea bottom.

Concerning zooplankton, a short look at the middle picture in Figures 3.10 and 3.11 checks the improvement due to the EnKS. During the first 100 days, the standard deviation is more controlled, and during the spring bloom, its value are lower. It is a general fact that the standard deviation takes greater values during the bloom. This could be explained this way, nonlinear effects are stronger with higher concentrations and lead to a spreading of the ensemble, therefore, during the bloom the variance of the ensemble will increase. The reverse effect is also true, with small values, nonlinear effects are less noticeable, so that the variance of the ensemble takes low values. Eventually, we note that zooplankton's standard deviation is controlled over the first 100 meters, since the effects of the EnKS are still noticeable at the mid-depth.

Finally, we study the standard deviation of nitrate nitrogen on the bottom pictures of Figures 3.10 and 3.11. As we expect it, the standard deviation of nitrate takes lower values during the bloom, when nitrate's concentration decreases. The difference between the EnKF and the EnKS is not as obvious as in the previous pictures. In order to know if sea surface observations of phytoplankton's concentration help control nitrate's concentration, we must not look at the spring bloom, where variances are naturally low, but before and after this bloom, when the concentration of nitrates increases or decreases rapidly. Looking at the first 100 days lead us to think that nitrate's concentration can be controlled, since improvements are noticeable even at 100 meters. As the difference between the EnKF and the EnKS is bound to decrease with time, it seems normal that improvements are not noticeable at the end of the year.

Figure 3.12 confirms the main points of our previous analysis. We would like to point out two facts. Firstly, on the top picture of Figure 3.12, the EnKS does not seem to give "smooth" results. This is because we chose a small variance for the simulation of phytoplankton's observations. Secondly, the comparison between the climatology results and the results with various data assimilation methods is a way to check how much better our analysed estimates are. Concerning the phytoplankton and the zooplankton, data assimilation performs a strong update with only sea surface observations of phytoplankton. However, concerning the nitrate, results are not so much better when data assimilation is performed, observing surface phytoplankton's concentration only.

Figure 3.13 presents the results of the EnKS when data assimilation is performed

Figure 3.10: Standard deviation of the EnKF applied to the 7-compartment model, observing phytoplankton's concentration at the sea surface.

Figure 3.11: Standard deviation of the EnKS applied to the 7-compartment model, observing phytoplankton's concentration at the sea surface.

Figure 3.12: Mean Square Errors of the EnKF and the EnKS applied to the 7-compartment model, observing phytoplankton's concentration at the sea-surface.

observing sea surface phytoplankton, with two different values for the measurement variances. This figure illustrates how important the measurement variance is. If the variance is too small, the EnKS will not be as smooth as its name says. However, if the variance is too large, we will lose precision, and the control of the ensemble spread will not be as good as expected.

3.3.3 Assimilating nitrate on the total depth

Figures 3.14 and 3.15 present the results when nitrate profiles on the total depth are assimilated with the EnKF and the EnKS respectively. Concerning the bottom pictures, which represent nitrate's concentration, the difference with a simple assimilation of sea surface phytoplankton is not very noticeable except at the very beginning. Nevertheless, the top and middle pictures of Figure 3.15, representing estimates of phytoplankton's and zooplankton's concentration seem to be more noisy. This is because nitrate's observations are quite accurate and spaced over the whole depth. Thus, they build a system with strong constraints, preventing the EnKS from being "smooth".

Figures 3.16 and 3.17 show the standard deviation of the ensemble when data assimilation is performed, observing nitrate's profiles, with the EnKF and the EnKS respectively. As we expect it, the nitrate's standard deviation is much lower than when sea surface phytoplankton is assimilated. Moreover, on the top pictures, which represent the phytoplankton's standard deviation, we are able to appreciate the impact of sea surface phytoplankton's observations. Although nitrate and phytoplankton are directly connected through the dynamical equations, nitrate's observations over the whole depth are not enough to prevent the ensemble from spreading when the EnKF is used. It confirms that phytoplankton's observations are necessary in order to control the spreading of the ensemble when phytoplankton's concentration quickly evolves. Concerning zooplankton, Figure 3.11 and 3.17 are a good illustration of a simple idea: the more intermediaries there are between the dynamical variable and the observations, the less the improvement. Zooplankton is connected to nitrate only through phytoplankton, so that when nitrate is observed, the ensemble spread is much more than when sea surface phytoplankton is measured.

Figure 3.18 sums up our different remarks. MSE for the zooplankton are similar, whether data assimilation is performed or not. Nevertheless, the EnKS, on the contrary to the EnKF, shows a real ability to control the spreading of phytoplankton on the top graph.

3.3.4 Assimilating phytoplankton on the total depth

In order to analyse how good our assimilation is when only sea surface phytoplankton's observations are available, we run our twin experiment with profiles of phytoplankton over the whole depth. Figures 3.19 and 3.20 present the results of the EnKF and the EnKS respectively. As the control on phytoplankton is tighter, the strong variations of the EnKF are more noticeable than in subsection 3.3.2. Both phytoplankton and zooplankton benefit from the larger number of observations, but nitrate does not seem to be better updated. This impression is confirmed by looking

Figure 3.13: Mean Square Errors of the EnKS applied to the 7-compartment model, observing phytoplankton's concentration at the sea-surface, with 2 different values for the observations' variance.

Figure 3.14: EnKF applied to the 7-compartment model, observing nitrate's concentration over the whole depth.

Figure 3.15: EnKS applied to the 7-compartment model, observing nitrate's concentration over the whole depth.

Figure 3.16: Standard deviation of the EnKF applied to the 7-compartment model, observing nitrate's concentration over the whole depth.

Figure 3.17: Standard deviation of the EnKS applied to the 7-compartment model, observing nitrate's concentration over the whole depth

Figure 3.18: Mean Square Errors of the EnKS applied to the 7-compartment model, observing nitrate's concentration over the whole depth

at the MSE on Figures 3.21 and 3.22.

Parameters	Symbol	Value for P	Value for Z	Value for Nn
Dynamical variance	var_{dyn}	0.00001	0.00001	0.00001
Initial variance	var_{ini}	0.0001	0.0001	0.000625
Measurement variance	var_{meas}	0.0001	0.0001	0.00001

Table 3.2: The numerical value of the variances used in the 7-compartment model.

Figure 3.19: EnKF, applied to the 7-compartment model, observing phytoplankton's concentration over the whole depth.

Figure 3.20: EnKS, applied to the 7-compartment model, observing phytoplankton's concentration over the whole depth.

Figure 3.21: MSE results, using the EnKF applied to the 7-compartment model, with three different types of observations.

Figure 3.22: MSE results, using the EnKS applied to the 7-compartment model, with three different types of observations.

The twin experiments we made on the 2 ecosystem models allow us to draw some conclusions about the performance of the EnKF and the EnKS.

Firstly, the improvement of the estimates due to assimilating data is very noticeable when the dynamical system reaches an unstable region such as the spring bloom. Moreover, in such a case, the results of the EnKS are much better than the EnKF: by carrying the information backward in time, the EnKS controls the spreading of the ensemble.

Secondly, the experiment made with the 7-compartment model confirms the first conclusions of the 3-compartment model. The update due to data assimilation is very important when the updated variable is directly connected to the observations (same variable, same time, same depth). The control an observation will have on the spreading of the ensemble decreases with depth or as the number of intermediary variables between the observations and the updated variable increases.

Thirdly, the EnKS proved to resist the nonlinearities of the dynamical models, when concentrations were high, such as during the spring bloom, or when they varied quickly. This point is very important to notice, since we assume indirectly that the dynamical system is linear, when we perform the variance minimizing method on each of the ensemble members.

Concerning data assimilation methods, although the EnKS is an important amelioration compared to the EnKF, it is not the best we can do. The EnKS still uses the variance minimizing method when it updates the ensemble members, even if we know that, theoretically, we should compute the Maximum Likelihood Estimate. Successful attempts have been made to use the Maximum Likelihood Estimate, but this method has not yet been applied to high dimensional state spaces. Only time, work and research will allow us to solve this problem and to make one more step towards the Truth.

Eventually, the results of the twin experiments open future perspectives, concerning ecosystems and more generally, operational oceanography. The presence of ocean color data, together with appropriate data assimilation methods will help developing a marine prediction system for biological parameters.

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